

Author-accepted manuscript of the article published in Nanotechnology (IOP Publishing). Final published version available at <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/46/31/312001>. This version is made available in compliance with IOP Publishing's self-archiving policy. It is not the publisher's formatted PDF and may contain minor differences from the final version.

Mechanisms of Hyperthermia in Magnetic Nanoparticles

Gonzalo Vallejo-Fernandez,^{,†,§} Oliver Whear,^{†,§} Alejandro G. Roca,,^{†,§} Susanna A. Hussain,[‡]
James Timmis,[‡] Vijay Patel,[‡] and Kevin O'Grady^{†,‡}.*

[†]Department of Physics, The University of York, York, YO10 5DD, UK

[‡]Liquids Research Ltd, Unit 7 Mentec, Deiniol Road, Bangor, LL57 2UP, UK

KEYWORDS: Hyperthermia, nanoparticles, magnetite/maghemite.

ABSTRACT: Magnetic hyperthermia is one of several approaches for cancer treatment currently under investigation. It has been demonstrated to reduce tumor size in animals and human beings. However a clear theoretical understanding of the origin of this phenomenon is still lacking. We report on a novel theoretical framework for magnetic hyperthermia. In this model we assume that 1) the suspensions consists on particles that follows log normal size distribution, 2) the hydrodynamic sizes are log normal distributed, 3) the dominating heating mechanism is size-dependent. Our model shows that the amount of heat generated by magnetic nanoparticles can be understood when both the physical and hydrodynamic size distributions for the samples are known to high accuracy. The model is validated by studying the magnetic, colloidal and heating properties of magnetite/maghemite nanoparticles of different sizes dispersed in solvents of different viscosity. It is shown that heating arising due to AC losses can be neglected with hysteresis loss being the dominant heating mechanism for the samples studies in this work. It is found that it is crucial to measure the specific absorption rate of samples only when embedded in a solid matrix

to avoid viscous heating effects and, hence, overestimating the heating performance of the particles.

MAIN TEXT

Magnetic hyperthermia occurring in colloids of magnetic nanoparticles has been demonstrated to reduce tumor size in human beings¹ Several heating mechanisms are possible, associated with susceptibility loss, hysteresis loss and viscous heating², however, at the present time the overall mechanism by which the heat is generated is not fully understood. Susceptibility loss occurs in superparamagnetic particles and has two relaxation processes associated with Néel reversal and Brownian rotation of the particles as they are in a liquid environment.³The Néel (τ_N) and Brownian (τ_B) relaxation times are given by

$$\tau_N = \frac{1}{f_0} \exp\left[\frac{KV(1-H/H_K)^2}{k_B T}\right] \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_B = \frac{3V_h \eta}{k_B T} \quad (2)$$

where $f_0 = 10^9 \text{s}^{-1}$, K is the anisotropy constant of the particles, V is the volume of the particles, H is the applied field, H_K is the anisotropy field, k_B is Boltzmann's constant and T is the temperature. Eq 2 for the Brownian relaxation is controlled by hydrodynamic parameters. Hence V_h is the hydrodynamic volume and η is the viscosity of the medium. The hydrodynamic volume can be defined as the volume of the particle/particles (if they are aggregated) and surfactants that coat the particles plus the solvent molecules adsorbed or entrapped

The existence of two relaxation times leads to a combined relaxation time τ given by

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_N \tau_B}{\tau_N + \tau_B} \quad (3)$$

Above a critical given size ($D_p(0)$) the particles will be blocked and hence hysteresis losses becomes the heating dominant mechanism. This critical diameter is given by⁴

$$D_p(0) = \left(\frac{6k_B T \ln(tf_0)}{\pi K} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

where t is the time of measurement. $D_p(0)$ denotes the critical size in zero field. Above $D_p(0)$ heating due to hysteresis loss will occur. For hyperthermia applications an AC field of up to 200Oe at a frequency of 100kHz is generally used.⁵ The low amplitude of the field will limit the fraction of blocked particles that undergo reversal and, hence, hysteresis heating. At 100 kHz the coercivity (H_c) variation with size is given by⁴,

$$H_c = H_K \left[1 - \left(\frac{9.21k_B T}{\pi K} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (5)$$

This means that particles above a given diameter ($D(H)$) will not contribute to either AC or hysteresis loss heating. The value of this diameter depends upon the applied field H and can be written as

$$D(H) = \left[1 - \frac{HM_s}{0.96K} \right]^{-2/3} D_p(0) \quad (6)$$

where M_s is the saturation magnetisation of the particles and the factor 0.96 arises due to the random distribution of easy axes i.e. $H_K = 0.96K/M_s$ ⁵. We assume that K is constant for all the particles within the size distribution. Only those particles with a diameter $D < D(H)$ will contribute to hysteresis loss heating. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the two critical diameters separating contributions to heating arising from AC, hysteresis losses and stirring.

For particles with $D > D(H)$ the moments cannot switch in the 200Oe field. The majority of the particles are not aligned with the solenoidal field and viscous heating due to stirring of the particles in the colloid will occur. At a frequency of 100kHz this effect, which will be more pronounced for aggregated particles, probably accounts for some of the anomalously large heating effects that have been reported⁶. The presence of a solenoidal field will also lead to the gradual alignment of bigger particles and aggregates thus accounting for non-linear heating rates that have been reported⁷. This leads to three contributions to the heat generated in the system: AC losses (P_{AC}), hysteresis loss (P_{hys}) and magnetic stirring (P_{stir}). The power generated through AC losses is given by⁸,

$$P_{AC} = \pi f \chi'' H^2 \quad (7)$$

where f is the frequency of measurement and χ'' is the complex part of the AC susceptibility. χ'' can be written as

$$\frac{\chi''}{\chi_0} = \frac{2\pi f \tau}{1 + (2\pi f \tau)^2} \quad (8)$$

where χ_0 is the DC initial susceptibility and τ is the combined relaxation time from superparamagnetic effects from Néel and Brownian effects. In real systems a distribution of particle and hydrodynamic volumes and, hence, relaxation times occurs given by

$$\tau_N^{eff} = \int_0^{V_p(0)} \tau_N(V) f(V) dV \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_B^{eff} = \int_0^{V_p(0)} \tau_B(V_h) f(V_h) dV_h \quad (10)$$

where τ_N^{eff} and τ_B^{eff} are the effective relaxation times, $f(V)$ is the distribution of physical volumes and $f(V_h)$ is the distribution of hydrodynamic volumes, $V_p(0)$ is the volume of a particle having a diameter $D_p(0)$ and $V_h(0)$ is the hydrodynamic volume of a particle having a physical diameter $D_p(0)$.

In the case of hysteresis heating the amount of heat generated is proportional to the frequency multiplied by the area of the loop. However, it is only the irreversible part of the magnetization that contributes to this effect. Since the particles are randomly oriented and, hence, their remanence is equal to $0.5M_s$, and only particles with a diameter such as $D_p(0) < D < D_p(H)$ are blocked and can be switched in the field H , P_{hys} can be written as

$$P_{hys} = 0.5M_s f \int_{V_p(0)}^{V_p(H)} H_c(V) V f(V) dV \quad (11)$$

where $V_p(H)$ is the volume of a particle having a diameter $D_p(H)$.

The calculation of the heat generated by the frictional drag on the particle (P_{stir}) is extremely complex. Firstly we have no value for the drag coefficient between a coated nanoparticle and the liquid although some approximation could be made. However the flow of the liquid around such particle will almost certainly be turbulent and hence none of the standard equations of hydrodynamics apply. Nonetheless magnetic stirring of the liquid will lead to a frictional effect but this effect is not only impossible to calculate but equally impossible to control. Note that at

10⁵Hz the stirring rate is 6x10⁶rpm. It may also lead to a lag between the alignment of the moment and the field which itself will create another form of magnetic heating similar to the susceptibility loss.

The amount of heat generated by magnetic nanoparticles is quantified normally in terms of the specific absorption rate (SAR) which represents the power generated by unit mass of magnetic material in the solution. Depending on the exact procedure followed to measure SAR, widely differing results may be obtained. Furthermore factors such as container shape and sample volume can lead to different SAR for the same particles.⁸ SAR is given by

$$SAR = C\phi \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \quad (12)$$

where C is the specific heat of the colloid, ϕ is the concentration of Fe and $\Delta T/\Delta t$ represents the heating rate. Equation 12 does not take into account the heat capacity of the sample holder. Whether the sample holder is made of glass, polycarbonate or another similar material, the heating of the sample holder will use a significant proportion of the power generated. Hence, it is crucial that all measurements are made using identical conditions in the same volume of sample. However, this also suggests that it might not be possible to compare measurements made in different measurement systems.

To test our model we have undertaken a study of the heating properties of ferrofluids containing magnetite/maghemite particles with different sizes and also suspended in carriers of different viscosity and wax.

All samples studied in this work were supplied by Liquids Research Ltd. The particles were prepared by the co-precipitation method with controlled growth conditions to give a narrow size distribution. The samples were dispersed in two solvents with different viscosities to study the

effect of the viscosity of the suspension on the heating properties of the samples. In particular the samples were dispersed in isoparaffin oils Isopar M and Isopar V, which have viscosities of 2.97 and 10.8 cP respectively. The samples were also dispersed in a wax to eliminate heating effects arising from Brownian relaxation of the particles and viscous heating.

The physical median particle size (D_m) for each sample was measured by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a 200keV JEOL 2011 TEM. Samples were prepared by placing one drop of a dilute suspension of the particles in hexane on a carbon coated grid and allowing the solvent to evaporate. Over 500 particles were measured a Zeiss particle size analyzer to ensure good statistics using. The data was fitted to a lognormal distribution. Measuring a large number of particles is essential to determine the standard deviation of the distribution (σ) accurately. Figures 2a, 2b and 2c show typical bright field TEM images for the samples studied in this work. Figure 2d shows the particle size distribution for each sample. The median particle size and standard deviation for each distribution are summarized in Table 1. As it can be observed in Figure 1 the particles are isolated from each other due to the oleic acid capping molecules. Also it is worth to remark the rounded shape of the particles. In the case of the largest particles it can be observed the presence of dimers and small aggregates.

Figure 2. TEM images (a,b,c) and particle size distributions (d) for samples studied in this work.

Dynamic Light Scattering (Malvern Instruments Zetasizer) was used to measure the hydrodynamic size distribution for each sample. The viscosity of the colloids was measured at 27°C using a Wells-Brookfield cone and plate viscometer. Details of the median hydrodynamic size (D_h) and the standard deviation of the distribution (σ_h) as well as the viscosity (η) results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Particle and Hydrodynamic Size Parameters for Samples Dispersed in Isopar M (blue cells) and Isopar V (red cells).

Sample	D_m (nm)	σ	η (cP)	D_h (nm)	σ_h
A	10.3	0.16		22	0.53
B	11.7	0.15	2.97	27	0.39
C	15.2	0.22		19	0.44
A	10.3	0.16		20	0.43
B	11.7	0.15	10.78	36	0.31
C	15.2	0.22		25	0.39

AC susceptibility measurements were carried out in a home made susceptometer at room temperature. Figure 3 shows the susceptibility loss peak given by the complex part of the AC susceptibility (χ'') for the samples dispersed in Isopar V.

Figure 3. Imaginary part of the AC susceptibility χ'' as a function of the frequency of measurement for samples dispersed in Isopar V.

The position of the AC loss peak varies over an order of magnitude for these samples. Interestingly, there is no monotonic variation of the position of the peak with the physical particle size. This highlights the importance of the distribution of hydrodynamic sizes when calculating AC losses. A rapid estimation of the critical size where Brownian relaxes faster than Neel for

magnetite particles suspended in Isopar V leads to a value of 10.1 nm so it supports the result pointed above. The solid lines in Fig. 3 are calculated fits Eq. 7, 8 and 9.

Figure 4 shows the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) for all samples as a function of the applied field. SAR was calculated using the increase in temperature of the sample during the first seconds after applying the alternating magnetic field. For Isopar M and Isopar V $C = 2206 \text{ J/kgK}$ and for wax $C = 2140 \text{ J/kgK}$. The concentration of particles in liquid was $\phi = 20 \text{ mg Fe/ml}$ for all samples. The frequency of measurement was kept constant at 111.5 kHz. From the data in Figure 3 at 111.5 kHz heating arising due to the AC losses for samples dispersed in Isopar V will be minimal ($\chi'' \sim 0$) and hence hysteresis loss would dominate. This is evidenced by the similar results obtained for all samples independently of the viscosity of the suspension as hysteresis loss does not depend upon the colloidal properties of the system studied. The samples embedded in wax show the poorest heating properties as heating due to stirring is removed. This result was previously observed by Hergt et al.⁹

Figure 4. Measured SAR values for samples dispersed in Isopar M (left), Isopar V (centre) and wax (right).

The critical size for superparamagnetic, $D_p(0)$ behavior at 111.5 kHz is 11.2nm. For samples studied in this work a significant fraction of the particle size distribution falls below this limit leading to no heating through hysteresis loss. We have also calculated the critical particle size that can be switched at the field of measurement at a frequency of 111.5kHz. Equation 6 yields: 11.6, 12.1, 12.6 and 13.2nm for an applied field of 63, 125, 188 and 250Oe respectively. Hence, at 250Oe only particles with a diameter such that $11.2\text{nm} < D < 13.2\text{nm}$ will contribute to hysteresis heating. This corresponds to 24%, 23% and 18% of the particles in samples A (10.3nm), B (11.7nm) and C (15.2nm), respectively. This explains the higher SAR ratio achieved for sample A (10.3nm) in the case of samples dispersed in wax. However, for samples dispersed in Isopar M the highest SAR value is obtained for sample B (11.7nm) at 250Oe. Using Eq. 11 hysteresis losses account for >90% of the heating arising from AC and hysteresis losses.

D_m (nm)	$D_p(0 \text{ Oe})$ (nm)	$D_p(63 \text{ Oe})$ (nm)	$D_p(125 \text{ Oe})$ (nm)	$D_p(188 \text{ Oe})$ (nm)	$D_p(250 \text{ Oe})$ (nm)	% Particles contribute to hysteresis
10.3						24
11.7	11.2	11.6	12.1	12.6	13.2	23
15.1						18

In conclusion heating arising in magnetic nanoparticles dispersed in solvents of different viscosity can be understood when the distributions of physical and hydrodynamic sizes are known to high accuracy. Measurements of samples dispersed in wax show that the contribution of stirring is about 30% of the heating effect. In order to obtain meaningful data, SAR values should be obtained from measurements of samples in a solid form. This is required to avoid viscous heating effects that may not occur in blood or in the tissue of tumors.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: gonzalo.vallejofernandez@york.ac.uk.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Authors would like to thank Nick Cramp and James Sagar for the measurement of the particle size distribution of the samples. OW acknowledges financial support from the Institute of Physics under the Top 40 work placements scheme. A. G. Roca acknowledges financial support from the Spanish Ministerio de Educación, through Programa Nacional de Movilidad de Recursos Humanos of Plan Nacional of I-D+i 2008-2011.

REFERENCES

1. (a) Jordan, A.; Scholz, R.; Wust, P.; Fähling, H.; Roland, F., Magnetic fluid hyperthermia (MFH): Cancer treatment with AC magnetic field induced excitation of biocompatible superparamagnetic nanoparticles. *J Magn Magn Mater* **1999**, *201* (1–3), 413-419; (b) Wust, P.; Hildebrandt, B.; Sreenivasa, G.; Rau, B.; Gellermann, J.; Riess, H.; Felix, R.; Schlag, P. M., Hyperthermia in combined treatment of cancer. *Lancet Oncol* **2002**, *3* (8), 487-97; (c) Laurent, S.; Dutz, S.; Häfeli, U. O.; Mahmoudi, M., Magnetic fluid hyperthermia: Focus on superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **2011**, *166* (1–2), 8-23.
2. Hergt, R.; Dutz, S.; Muller, R.; Zeisberger, M., Magnetic particle hyperthermia: nanoparticle magnetism and materials development for cancer therapy. *J Phys-Condens Mat* **2006**, *18* (38), S2919-S2934.
3. Bean, C. P.; Livingston, J. D., Superparamagnetism. *J Appl Phys* **1959**, *30* (4), S120-S129.
4. Cullity, B. D., *Introduction to Magnetic Materials* **1972**.
5. Jordan, A.; Scholz, R.; Maier-Hauff, K.; van Landeghem, F. K. H.; Waldoefner, N.; Teichgraeber, U.; Pinkernelle, J.; Bruhn, H.; Neumann, F.; Thiesen, B.; von Deimling, A.; Felix, R., The effect of thermotherapy using magnetic nanoparticles on rat malignant glioma. *J Neuro-Oncol* **2006**, *78* (1), 7-14.

6. Gladman, A. S.; Davidson, S. R. H.; Easty, A. C.; Joy, M. L.; Sherar, M. D., Infrared thermographic SAR measurements of interstitial hyperthermia applicators: errors due to thermal conduction and convection. *International Journal of Hyperthermia* **2004**, *20* (5), 539-555.
7. Huang, S.; Wang, S. Y.; Gupta, A.; Borca-Tasciuc, D. A.; Salon, S. J., On the measurement technique for specific absorption rate of nanoparticles in an alternating electromagnetic field. *Measurement Science and Technology* **2012**, *23* (3), 035701.
8. Goya, G. F.; Grazu, V.; Ibarra, M. R., Magnetic Nanoparticles for Cancer Therapy. *Curr Nanosci* **2008**, *4* (1), 1-16.
9. Hergt, R.; Hiergeist, R.; Zeisberger, M.; Glöckl, G.; Weitschies, W.; Ramirez, L. P.; Hilger, I.; Kaiser, W. A., Enhancement of AC-losses of magnetic nanoparticles for heating applications. *J Magn Magn Mater* **2004**, *280* (2–3), 358-368.